

INDIRECT TRANSLATION AS NORMATIVE MEDIATION IN VIDEO GAME LOCALISATION: THE CASE OF JAPANESE TO LATIN AMERICAN SPANISH LOCALISATION VIA ENGLISH AS A PIVOT LANGUAGE

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While indirect translation has been acknowledged in Translation Studies, it has often remained marginal, limiting engagement with its contemporary and increasingly prevalent manifestations. One such manifestation is indirect translation in the modern localisation industry. Despite the global circulation of non-English media, localisation workflows are frequently structured around English as a central pivot language, relegating other languages to peripheral positions. This configuration becomes particularly notorious in the case of Japanese video game localisation. Industry practice normally involves an initial localisation from Japanese into English, where the majority of interpretive, temporal, and economic resources are concentrated, while subsequent localisations into other languages are then produced under tighter constraints and typically on the basis of the English version, with limited or no direct reference to the Japanese source text (O'Hagan & Mangiron, 2013). Drawing on Descriptive Translation Studies and the concept of norm-governed translation (Toury, 1995; Chesterman, 1997), this paper examines how English pivot translations function as sites of interpretive stabilisation within this workflow. Focusing on cases where Latin American Spanish is the final target language, it explores how decisions relating to tone, register, characterization, and explicitation are established at the pivot stage and transmitted downstream. Rather than presupposing specific cultural losses, the study adopts a practitioner-informed perspective to describe how indirect translation conditions the interpretive options available to later translators. It further considers how industry mechanisms such as scripts, templates, and style guides render earlier translational negotiations opaque to downstream agents (Schäffner, 2012). In this sense, pivot translation is approached as a form of cultural rewriting shaped primarily by implicit norms rather than explicit ideological positioning (Lefevere, 1992). By framing indirect translation as a routine, norm-governed practice embedded in localisation pipelines, this paper contributes to a more nuanced understanding of mediated translation in global game distribution (Even-Zohar, 1990).

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